
Series: PHYSICS

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Faraday's equation and law of electromagnetic induction - theory and practice

Annotation

It can be said that induction, discovered by Faraday, was the main reason for the emergence of Maxwell's system of equations. She entered this system as one of these equations. Based on this equation, the law of electromagnetic induction is formulated. It is shown that this law should not be applied in practical electrical engineering.

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1. Introduction

Electromagnetic induction, discovered by Faraday, served as the basis for Maxwell in the formation of his system of equations and entered this system as one of these equations. The modern tradition allows this equation to be used separately, as a physical law independent of the system of equations. But such isolation of one equation from a system of equations contradicts mathematics. We will show that electromagnetic induction is a consequence of the entire system of Maxwell's equations, which as a whole can be considered as a physical law.

The phenomenon of electromagnetic induction was found experimentally by Faraday and written by Maxwell strictly as an equation of electromagnetic induction in differential form

$$\text{rot}(E) = -\frac{\partial B}{\partial t} = -\mu \frac{\partial H}{\partial t}. \quad (1)$$

where E, B, H, μ are electrical strength, magnetic induction, strength, absolute permeability.

The same phenomenon can be written in integral form as

$$\varepsilon = \frac{d\Phi}{dt}, \quad (2)$$

where ε is the magnitude of the electromotive force (EMF) in a closed loop, which limits the surface S through which the magnetic flux Φ passes, which is the integral of the induction B over this surface:

$$\Phi = \iiint_S B dS. \quad (3)$$

The direction of the electromotive force is determined by Lenz's law. Definition (2) is usually called the law of electromagnetic induction. It follows from it that

1. EMF can only occur in a closed circuit,
2. The magnetic flux in the magnetic core can create an EMF in any circuit closed around it, no matter how far the circuit is from the core.

The law of electromagnetic induction in this form is presented by theoretical electrodynamics to practicing engineers. Of course, they find a way out of the situation, but how could such a law appear and exist?!

In integral form, equation (1) is replaced by an equation of the form

$$\int_L E \cdot dL = -\frac{d}{dt} \int_S \mu H \cdot dS, \quad (4)$$

which is equivalent to equation (2). From (4) also follows (1). But in the general case, (1) does not imply (4)! The transition from differential to integral form is based on the Kelvin-Stokes theorem, which considers a vector field that has continuous first-order partial derivatives in a given area. The field of magnetic induction $B = \mu H$ around the said core does not obey the Kelvin-Stokes theorem, since the coefficient μ changes abruptly in this region. Therefore, the law of electromagnetic induction in integral form has no practical meaning. Note that, in the same way, the theorem on the circulation of a magnetic field in integral form has no practical meaning when a dielectric appears in a vacuum. And in general, Maxwell's equations in integral form are applicable only in exotic cases.

Therefore, further we will consider how to find the Faraday induction EMF based on Maxwell's equations in differential form, including, of course, the Faraday induction formula (1).

2. The simplest transformer

On fig. 1 shows the simplest transformer for further mathematical description, which consists of two pieces of wire WG and WL, placed in a magnetically conductive tube M. It is assumed (although this is not shown in the figure) that this tube is closed and, therefore, the magnetic flux from it is not radiated into space, i.e. not consumed. The wire WG is connected to the generator G and conduction current I_G flows through it. In this case, a magnetic intensity H_G arises on the surface of the wire WG. The magnetic flux Φ , created by this intensity, propagates through the pipe M and creates a magnetic intensity H_L on the surface of the wire WL. This tension creates a conduction current I_L in the wire WL, which enters the electrical load L. Thus, the power P is transferred from the generator G to the load L, and the propagates through the pipe M the power P and the flow $\Phi - (P\Phi)$.

Fig. 1.

Some statements need clarification. Together with the conduction current, an electromagnetic wave and an electromagnetic energy flux equal to the generator power propagate in the wire. This means that there is a solution to Maxwell's equations for a wire with conduction current. One of these equations has the form

$$\text{rot}(H) = I. \quad (1)$$

It follows from this that the magnetic strength on the surface of the wire is determined as a function of the conduction current.

Another equation in this system is

$$\operatorname{rot}E = -\mu \frac{\partial H}{\partial t}. \quad (2)$$

It follows from it that there is an electrical strength in the wire if there is a variable magnetic intensity on the surface of the wire. When there are strengths E and H in the wire, there is an electromagnetic wave and a flow of electromagnetic energy equal to the power consumed by the load.

When magnetic strength appears on the surface of the wire connected to the generator, a flow of energy appears in the magnetic tube, circulating through the tube. In this case, an electromagnetic wave and a flow of electromagnetic energy arise in the tube, which circulates in the tube along with the magnetic flux. (This phenomenon is similar to the fact that the flow of electromagnetic energy in the wire propagates along with the electric current.) This flow has an insignificant value - the idling power. The same power is generated by the generator. When the load circuit is closed, a power consumer appears and the power circulating through the pipe branches off from the pipe into a wire connected to the load. In essence, all the generator power flows through the pipe to the load.

All these processes are described as the solution of Maxwell's equations for a wire with an alternating conduction current and for a magnetic circuit. These solutions were found in [1] and briefly presented in the appendices. It follows from them that all currents and strengths in such a transformer are determined with a known voltage at the input of the wire WG and a known load power L.

We can change the section of the pipe and/or change the length of the pipe. In this case, the magnetic flux Φ will change. However, the result of the solution will not change - it depends on the transmitted power and the voltage at the generator output. In this case, [the law of electromagnetic induction is clearly violated](#).

3. Experiments

Above is the theory. But some author of a textbook on electrodynamics or a teacher of lectures on electrodynamics worked out over many years can irritably throw it aside (his irritation is understandable). Therefore, let us consider experiments confirming this theory.

The first experiment is shown in [2] - see fig. 2. The author considers a magnetically conductive torus with a bifilar winding under alternating voltage. The winding shields the magnetic field of the torus and does not have its own field, because. is bifilar. Therefore, there is no magnetic field outside this coil. In the "yellow circuit", according to the law of

electromagnetic induction, an emf should be induced. induction, since a magnetic flux passes inside this circuit. The author asks the question: "How does the circuit know that the magnetic flux changes within the circuit?" The author is looking for an answer to this question in solving Maxwell's equations. It turns out that the magnetic induction outside the coil is 10^{-16} of the induction inside the coil. Obviously, such an induction cannot create an emf. inside the contour.

Fig. 2.

The second experiment is carried out daily, many times and everywhere: in the core of a transformer, the magnetic flux keeps its amplitude almost constant when the load changes. But when the load changes, the amplitude of the emf changes in the secondary winding. This emf varies over a wide range, although, according to the law of electromagnetic induction, it must retain its value at a constant magnetic flux. But that doesn't happen...

Fig. 3

The third experiment is shown in [3] - see fig. 3. The author considers a transformer with a long magnetic core and writes down the equations of the law of electromagnetic induction for two circuits A and B - see the upper and lower equations in fig. 3. Further, the author draws a completely fair conclusion from these equations: there must be a large

magnetic flux between the horizontal sections of the magnetic circuit - see the blue arrow. The author's face does not show satisfaction from such a conclusion, but it has nothing to do with he: such is the theory. Obviously, there is no "blue" magnetic flux, and this can be verified by direct measurement. Therefore, the [law of electromagnetic induction is wrong](#).

It follows from these experiments that the considered [emf induction is NOT a consequence of the law of electromagnetic induction \(1.2\)](#), but is a consequence of Faraday's induction equation (1.1).

Application 1. Solution of Maxwell's equations for electric wire

In [1, chapter 2p] it is shown that in a wire with a sinusoidal conduction current there is an electromagnetic wave, which is a solution of the Maxwell equations of the form

$$\text{rot}(E) + \frac{\mu}{c} \frac{\partial H}{\partial t} = 0, \quad (1)$$

$$\text{rot}(H) - J = 0, \quad (2)$$

$$\text{div}(E) = 0, \quad (3)$$

$$\text{div}(H) = 0, \quad (4)$$

where E are electrical strengths, H are magnetic strengths, J are conduction currents, μ is magnetic permeability. In cylindrical coordinates, the projections of strengths and currents have the form:

$$H_{r\cdot} = h_r(r) \text{si}, \quad (9)$$

$$H_{\varphi\cdot} = h_{\varphi}(r) \text{co}, \quad (10)$$

$$H_{z\cdot} = h_z(r) \text{co}, \quad (11)$$

$$E_{r\cdot} = e_r(r) \text{co}, \quad (12)$$

$$E_{\varphi\cdot} = e_{\varphi}(r) \text{si}, \quad (13)$$

$$E_{z\cdot} = e_z(r) \text{si}, \quad (14)$$

$$J_{r\cdot} = j_r(r) \text{si}, \quad (16)$$

$$J_{\varphi\cdot} = j_{\varphi}(r) \text{co}, \quad (17)$$

$$J_{z\cdot} = j_z(r) \text{co}, \quad (18)$$

$$\text{co} = \cos(\alpha\varphi + \chi z + \omega t), \quad (19)$$

$$\text{si} = \sin(\alpha\varphi + \chi z + \omega t), \quad (20)$$

where $h(r), e(r), j(r)$ are functions of the coordinate r , and α, χ, ω are constants, which are related by the following relations:

$$k = \sqrt{\frac{\sigma c}{\mu \omega}}, \quad (21)$$

$$\chi = \sqrt{\frac{\sigma\mu\omega}{c}}, \quad (22)$$

$$e_z = Ar^{-\alpha}, \quad (23)$$

$$e_\varphi = e_r = Br^{1-\alpha}, \quad (24)$$

$$B = \frac{\chi A}{2(1-\alpha)}, \quad (25)$$

$$h_r = ke_r, \quad (26)$$

$$h_\varphi = -ke_\varphi. \quad (27)$$

$$h_z = -ke_z, \quad (28)$$

$$j_r = \sigma e_r, \quad (29)$$

$$j_\varphi = \sigma e_\varphi, \quad (30)$$

$$j_z = \sigma e_z, \quad (31)$$

$$0 < \alpha < 1, \quad (32)$$

where, in turn, σ is the electrical conductivity of the wire, and the coefficients α, A are calculated depending on the voltage on the wire and the active power transmitted through it. This power is determined by a formula of the form

$$P = B^2 \frac{ck}{4} \cdot \frac{R^{4-2\alpha}}{2-\alpha}. \quad (33)$$

Application 2. Solution of Maxwell's equations for the magnetic circuit.

In [1, Chapter 3] it is shown that in a magnetic circuit with a sinusoidal magnetic flux there is an electromagnetic wave, which is a solution of the Maxwell equations of the form

$$\text{rot}(E) + \frac{\mu}{c} \frac{\partial H}{\partial t} = 0, \quad (1)$$

$$\text{rot}(H) - \frac{\varepsilon}{c} \frac{\partial E}{\partial t} = 0, \quad (2)$$

$$\text{div}(E) = 0, \quad (3)$$

$$\text{div}(H) = 0, \quad (4)$$

where ε is the permittivity. In cylindrical coordinates, the projections of strength have the form:

$$H_{r.} = h_r(r) \text{co}, \quad (9)$$

$$H_{\varphi.} = h_\varphi(r) \text{si}, \quad (10)$$

$$H_{z.} = h_z(r) \text{si}, \quad (11)$$

$$E_{r.} = e_r(r) \text{si}, \quad (12)$$

$$E_{\varphi.} = e_\varphi(r) \text{co}, \quad (13)$$

$$E_{z.} = e_z(r) \text{co}, \quad (14)$$

$$\text{co} = \cos(\alpha\varphi + \chi z + \omega t), \quad (15)$$

$$\text{si} = \sin(\alpha\varphi + \chi z + \omega t), \quad (16)$$

where $h(r), e(r)$ are functions of the coordinate r , and α, χ, ω are constants, which are related by the following relations:

$$k = \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\mu}}, \quad (17)$$

$$\chi = \frac{\omega}{c} \sqrt{\mu\varepsilon}, \quad (18)$$

$$e_z = Ar^{-\alpha}, \quad (19)$$

$$e_r = -\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\alpha}{\chi r} + \frac{\chi r}{\alpha} \right) e_z, \quad (20)$$

$$e_\varphi = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\alpha}{\chi r} - \frac{\chi r}{\alpha} \right) e_z, \quad (21)$$

$$h_r = ke_r, \quad (22)$$

$$h_\varphi = -ke_\varphi, \quad (23)$$

$$h_z = -ke_z, \quad (24)$$

where, in turn, the coefficients α, A are calculated depending on the magnetomotive force in the magnetic circuit and the active power transmitted through it. This power is determined by a formula of the form

$$P_z = A^2 \frac{ck}{8} f(R, \chi, \alpha), \quad (25)$$

where

$$f(R, \chi, \alpha) = R^{-2\alpha} \left(\left(\frac{\alpha}{\chi} \right)^2 \frac{\chi^2}{2\alpha} + \left(\frac{\chi}{\alpha} \right)^2 \frac{\alpha}{4-2\alpha} R^4 \right). \quad (26)$$

References

1. Khmelnik Solomon I. Inconsistency Solution of Maxwell's Equations. Version 19, pp. 1–378, 2021. "MiC" - Mathematics in Computer Corp, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5796226>
2. А. Щетников. Парадокс трансформатора. Новосибирский Государственный Университет. Физический факультет. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3P56ZQ2eZWk&t=626s>
3. Андрей Щетников. Вектор Умова-Пойнтинга*4. Новосибирский Государственный Университет. Физический факультет, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nFQGef5uFqU&t=356s>